

THE PHENOMENON OF DEMOCRACY AND THE STATE IN THE IDEAL SOCIETY

Individual and Society
Democracy and Democratic Understanding
State, Personality of the State, State and Society

Article Application Date: 2024

Article Publication Date: 2024 Article Type: Review Article

To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 6-06, 2024, p. 200– 222 - 0099-0001-2406-03007.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") "EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform." ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

""• *Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with*

1

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic" ("CURRENT SCIENCE ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") Science Georgia") journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

"The journal will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

- The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies -Current Science Georgia")*

"• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days."

("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Serhat ERDUR

PhD Student

St. Clements University

Political Science and

Public Administration

MSB

Ocid ID: 0009-0009-4351-3483

Email:

srhdr90@gmail.com

Abstract

The goal of this essay is to investigate the phenomena of a valid state with a democratic understanding in the ideal society model and provide a method.

In this context, human beings, as social beings, are a link in the social chain, affect society positively or negatively, and constitute the basis of cultural products; the effects of culture on the formation of an ideal society, which includes all the values such as beliefs, measures, values, principles, rules followed, styles of action, etc., that bring individuals into communities, separate communities from one another, and protect them from falling into a heap, a mass

On the other hand, the understanding of the state changes in democratic or anti-democratic directions with social reaction; in the ideal society model, the democratic state approach is considered superior; it will be concluded that the personality of the state and the state power must be limited by society in order to prevent the use of public power by a group in the state-society relationship.

Keywords: *Individual and society, human being as a social being, cultural product, society as a vital condition of human being, state of law, democratic state understanding, anti-democratic approach, personality of the state, state-government, state-society, limited state power, functional facts, evolution*

INTRODUCTION

Since his inception, man has attempted to connect with and comprehend himself as well as the society in which he lives, in order to discover the perfect state structure that it has established. Since ancient times, there has been a concept of humanity, a perspective of society, and an interpretation of the state and democracy. Scientific branches, examination, and study areas have been identified within the historical flow. In contrast to the material world, the ideas of individual-society-state are fluid, ambiguous, and dynamic, which has delayed technical growth in the material realm. Undoubtedly, the viewpoint of people who present views and ideas in these domains, as well as the meaning that this knowledge confers on the notions, have played and continue to play an important part in this.

Individual-society psychological assessments remain confusing in this day and age. However, with the world's biotechnology breakthrough, the new direction necessitates revisiting lost societal notions and challenges.

Psycho-social ideas in the past and today have not developed a consistent pattern, ideology, and knowledge of religion, or universal facts. It is interpreted differently depending on societal value judgments, geographical area considerations, and competing and conflicting worldviews. Many different points of view have evolved as sociologists, psychologists, anthropologists, and ethnologists, who draw their methodologies from the principles on which their concepts are

founded, attempt to obtain conclusions based on the features of the cross-section of society under consideration. However, civilizations with a wide range of cultural aspects, such as language, literature, history, art, customs, habits, shared experiences, lifestyles, and ways of thinking, are distinguished by their unique qualities. Although the progressive transition of these distinctions into convergence is required by the world's new tendencies, it is true that they persist as internal dynamics of people and societies.

Just as a person expresses himself in his society and distinguishes himself from others, societies are distinguishable from one another by the principles of the universe of existence, which is reflected in societal behavior. If these ideals degrade or vanish, the move to a more dynamic society will speed up. Many communities, throughout time and space, have undergone similar interactions and metamorphoses. Civilizations formed throughout history in China, India, Egypt, Central Asia, South America, the Mediterranean, and the Aegean were times when a civilization that was an organized power acquired and extended influence by its distinctive ideals. It was founded on leaving a lasting legacy.

Civilizations that developed in big water basins in ancient times are examples of society's potential to evolve in a proper setting. Throughout history, civilizations have sought for efficacy with the goal of preserving their existence as distinct systems. This has become feasible because to the personality that society may bestow on people. Individuals and societies are structured with a network of rules based on their unique features, and as a result, they have created normative norms that define their traits. As a result, the material components offered by society include population unification, technology, and the economy; nevertheless, as a spiritual element, human people expose the truth of society via their value judgments and behavior patterns. Every civilization has a unique structure.

Individuals may be understood by observing how their personality manifests itself in the outer environment. Similarly, cultures may be understood by their social behaviors. Societies, like persons, fluctuate; they are not fixed, immovable things.

A. Individual and Society

1) Human as a Social Being

Humans exist in a natural, biological, and geographical environment that supports their survival. It, like all living things, has a reaction to defend and sustain itself. According to Malatyalı and Hititlerde Sosyal Yapı (2005), socializing is essential for the development of both individuals and society as a whole.

The development of emotions, the capacity to disclose personal talents, the concept of self, the development of personality, and the ability to be rational have all contributed to the quest for the right environment needed by one's own structure, as well as the ability to give meaning to this throughout time.

Man has the capacity and need to think and express himself, and he has began to do so via language, which has become the foundation of communal existence and the fabric of the cultural framework. Family formation, the tiny core of society, arose out of biological need. These are the foundations that support man's feeling of social belonging.

Furthermore, desire, emotion, propensity, will, and other comparable phenomena exist both as content and as social event dynamics. However, these ambiguous events are not caused by direct psychosocial or psychological causes. The dynamic social field surely has a significant impact on their development and purpose.

It is feasible to argue that the views and actions of an individual developing a personality bear the imprint of society. A person who has lost his or her individuality lacks human traits. Individuality is not spontaneous, as shown by the intimate link between the observable change in the person and the societal and environmental context.

The concept of community is described in several ways. According to one viewpoint, man's urge to live in society, known as social desire, stems from his proclivity to seek out someone who is like to him. According to one viewpoint, it is necessary to achieve individual and society interests. Another explanation is that it stems from a sense of social solidarity produced by people's similar and diverse demands. However, throughout history, humans have lived together. Despite its basic examples, the idea that people live in isolated communities apart

from civilization is impossible. People's existence depends on their social relationships. This is also a communal talent (Malatyali, 2006).

2) Human as a Link in the Chain of Society

Man cannot exist alone. It is seen as the consequence of human creation. The normal fundamental structure of the human species is inherited. Chemical signals sent by reproductive cells coincide with the genetic pattern of heredity and inheritance. While the individual's thought potential, which is a hereditary product, grows spontaneously via genetic inheritance, thought formation is influenced by environmental and educational circumstances comparable to those of their predecessors.

Humans are subject to the rule of continuation of life and race, and they constitute the most basic social organization, the family. The physio-psychic structure determines the occurrence and duration of connections between opposite sexes. The survival of humans, like all living things, is the result of strong instinct. This emotion, which originates in the tissues and psychological depths, is a kind of conscious conduct. Differences between the sexes are the logical result of rules followed. As a consequence, they complement one another mentally, physiologically, and economically. This involves integrating the social group into a family and preparing the setting for the new kid.

The family was not formed because of the man's envy, nor was it formed because of the mother's desire to care for her kid and give socioeconomic stability. Family occurs in several forms, ranging from the most rudimentary to the most advanced. The family, which is shown as a mental and biological requirement by the presence of two distinct genders and the fact that the infant is vulnerable and requires care, is a social reality that exists in all communities.

Human newborns go through a protracted developmental phase. Babies raised in institutions where all of their physical needs are met due to their psychosocial nature are unable to develop due to a lack of love (this situation is also seen in vertebrate animals), and as they grow older, they fall behind in terms of intelligence, language, and speech, and are less capable of establishing social relationships. Behavioral abnormalities and imbalances emerge in persons

who live distant from their social circles. To operate correctly, the human brain requires regular stimulus. This is only achievable in a social group and setting. Another major component that influences an individual's growth and existence is their social, psychological, biological, and physical surroundings. Humans need continuous adaptation training and aid for adaptation. According to Schofield (1972), Westermack and Briffault's statements are not supported by scientific evidence.

Ethnographic and anthropological facts do not support the concept that the early humans lived in flocks with the freedom to engage in irregular sexual encounters. However, the theories that the polygamous family existed as a result of the differentiation of ownership and power in the formation of the family and that it evolved into a monogamous family have lost their reality with the family form observed in primitive human community life in some parts of the world. The monogamous family structure appears in the early stages of society.

3) The Condition of Man's Existence is Society

Man is a reality, not only an unconscious component and shadow of the social organization. It is the epicenter of emotion, cognition, function, and action. It is one of the most dynamic aspects of civilization. Individuals' psychological and economic requirements shaped the organization's changeable, complicated structure. Individuals cannot be denied their useful roles. It is nonsensical to consider a social group without an individual. Society is both a unit and a system. Social reality cannot be defined only by social, geographical, biological, or psychological aspects.

Society is neither a bio-organic whole, as biologists say, nor a machine whole, as mechanists claim, nor an event to which the reason of everything is assigned, as sociologists claim (Sorokin 1972).

Social life entails demonstrating a sense of mutual interaction and influence. The social events that result from these are movements that involve a wide range of occurrences, such as emotional and cognitive commonalities that arise from people's oneness.

Social events are events that offer many features such as religion, language, family, morality, art, economics, and state, allowing people to live a healthy life in society and being created by their collective existence. Individuals find these truths, which are a necessary byproduct of societal conditions, freely accessible in society. As social truths, they exist before and beyond individuals.

While society prepares its youngsters for themselves, it also impacts its members in many aspects of their life. It provides them with the behavioral and cognitive models they need to safeguard themselves, their culture, and their future. Use the pressure approach as required. As a result, each person exclusively interacts with others from his or her own community and culture. At some point, social events occur outside of the person and have coercive and damning qualities.

4) Society is a System, Not a Mass

Society is a system. Social units indicate a system state. Every social group functions as both an organization and a social system. Family and religious groupings are virtually all significant and rational social entities. The social system is a functioning network created by the harmonious interaction of its constituents and subsystems. Continuous interactions have an effect on the events, people, and groups they affect. The durability of human relationships and trade channels is seen as the primary cause for social contact and the establishment of functional networks. Social life is made up of three major networks of connections and exchanges. Functional linkages persist within the context of a larger system. As a result, every structured unit, system, and union influences the form and direction of these linkages. According to Beer (1965), society is a system rather than a mass.

Society did not emerge spontaneously, by human instinct alone, or via individual thought. It was produced as a consequence of its own internal energy. This is the actuality of protection against pressures from the individual's biological and psychological constitution, natural circumstances, and external social groupings or societies.

There is material and spiritual distinction throughout society. Internal social energy gives this. Organization is the organization of the human element in several dimensions, such as time and space. Coercive energy is essential for the units of such a social organism to function inside a system.

Society's social distinction and stratification are the product of its internal processes. Individual age differences, character, moods, mental and physical psychic disparities, and race-environment differences are all dynamic social structural components that contribute to social divergence and the release of social energy.

Individuals and social organizations behave instinctively to safeguard their own survival. Social energy and the survival instinct drive civilization to change. With the demands of external society, new differentiation and kinds arise. This organization, which is the arrangement of units based on a certain model, allows the state to channel the social group that wields political power in the direction indicated by the social model.

Society, a group of individuals who think and believe in living together, demonstrates that it is a system rather than a mass by giving rise to social organizations that express themselves on this issue.

5) Society Exists with its Culture

Societies are groups organized around shared views and ideals. Wherever there is a distinct example of a society, there is always a society integrated inside its own autonomous set of values. The core behavioral concepts, patterns, and institutions that make up the structure of any community revolve around objectives that are important to the people of that community, as well as traits that draw them together. This scenario shapes the identity of the community. For example, this integrity is what differentiates Turkish, British, and Arab cultures. Every group that possesses this totality reflects this meaning, which is plainly obvious in its own behavior and culture in the shape of a perspective, idea, or emotion, and passes it along from generation to generation. In other words, people live in a culture that is peculiar to their

civilization. Individuals share a culture that is entire. An individual's life is formed by his own society and its values.

The cultural principles of the society are derived from the family, school, and other communities with whom we interact. Basic personality features surround the individual in this manner. As a result, no two cultures are exactly same.

A country cannot be formed without geography and history. A country is developed via the historical process of integrating and integrating individuals living on a specific piece of territory across generations, as well as the recognition of their uniqueness from other groups.

Individuals acquire personality within their communities, and countries may gain personality worldwide via national culture. The fact that the values of cultural patterns are not national implies that they are anti-national and hence national on behalf of another civilization. According to Adivar (1969), Talmud is deeply ingrained in Jewish, British, French, and Arab cultures and cannot be separated.

Societies are not sluggish, uninteresting, development-resistant, or unchanging entities. It is obligated to alter and refresh itself in response to the ever-changing and evolving circumstances of existence. Opposing this flux and change is suicide. However, reform should not be undertaken with the intention of denying them. It is vital to modify the principles and cultural norms that have transformed society from a herd to a conscious and powerful unity. Throwing aside these cultural norms because time has rendered them worthless or driving them in this direction implies allowing their breakdown into the body of another civilization. Change, which is the result of life, entails challenges that must be handled. Societies that are unable to handle this dilemma will inevitably face a catastrophe.

Cultural aspects exist as a totality. Society's existence is sustained by knowledge and the preservation of the entire. Those who rule the state decide their society's personal position amid other civilizations in this cultural environment.

B. Democracy and Democratic Understanding

1) Democratization

Democracy is a form of governance in which people form political parties and vote in elections, thereby taking over the government, and the government is constrained by law. There is a tight relationship between the degree of civilization attained by civilizations, the democratization process, and the superstructure that forms the organic structure of the state and society. Although it is linked to modernity, democracy, and human rights, its historical development varies each nation.

Political life evolves via the free development and operation of political forces. Assembly and other constitutional bodies, legal regulations, and institutional order make up the framework of democracy. Openness and pluralism are important truths. A culture of criticism, oversight, and discussion is how democracy should function.

Democracy either exists or doesn't. It must occur somewhere in social life (Blackburn, 1972).

Democracy is not the same as personal autonomy. It is especially not a personal or dynastic sovereignty founded on a legislative majority. Individual and group autonomy contradicts the core of democracy. Supporting individual and group sovereignty has long been seen as a way out for individuals who reject democratic norms.

Democracy is not a weapon for authorities to get additional benefits from the democratic environment.

Those who oppose democratization are both adversaries and proponents of democracy. Those who support democracy based on social rank and self-interest may abuse the public. However, sensitive public opinion, an aware public, and the media as an information tool must be used to avoid this exploitation. Democracy cannot thrive or be sustained in any other manner.

2) Democracy and Equality

While mankind is experiencing dynamic and fast change, it will also be successful in putting it into reality when the balance created by democracy between rulers and the governed, as well as the truth that individuals have inalienable rights and are born equal, are acknowledged.

The twenty-first century heralded a new era in human history. People of all races and genders are treated equally by United Nations declarations and international accords. Democracies aim to promote equality. The unfettered expression of ideas by minds free of dictatorial training has spread via mass media. This is the result of democratic conditions (Boratav, 1973).

Equality is one of the foundational principles of democracy. The most important thing is the right to equal benefits without advantages. If the idea of equality grants certain rulers special privileges, it indicates that an aristocratic minority wields power for the good of the class. It is understandable that government personnel benefit differentially because of their standing. However, owing to position, benefits other than this particular condition produce material and moral corruption in society, erode faith in democracy, and eliminate the potential to profit from democracy's blessings. Unequal advantages that shock the public conscience lead to widespread revolutions.

It is in the nature of the people to reject the ruling class's authority, to refuse to accept their advantages, and to think that every citizen has the right to live fearlessly and equitably, according to human decency.

3) Democracy and Freedom of Thought

Throughout history, humanity have fought for the freedom of thought and belief, as well as the ability to express and distribute their ideas. International agreements have been used to make efforts to ensure that all people have access to these rights, which are now contained in constitutions. Adopting an idea and believing in it are considered basic rights. Not being condemned or punished has been seen as a supplementary right. The contemporary state, with its democratic orientation, seeks to safeguard itself not just from ideas but also against acts (Boratav, 1973).

Although people think differently, they have created an environment in the democratic system in which they can coexist, where they are not condemned for their beliefs, where they develop tolerance and tolerance for opposing views, where forcing their own views is not tolerated, where ideas can be expressed as desired, and where people can be free in their thoughts and beliefs.

Humanity has suffered greatly because of such an environment. Liberation from religious and nonreligious movement dogmas required effort. The mind-science pair, which doubts, questions, critiques, and orients toward the truth, has created the free thinking environment of democracy by relinquishing the power source of political authority to the will of the people (Bouthoul, 1975).

Democracy has evolved into a regime that allows for the exchange of opposing viewpoints and instills a sense of humanity in its citizens.

4) Political and Social Democracy

For many years, the supremacy of economic forces has kept democracy abstract, as have its formal rituals. Features: In the 1920s, political and social democracy were influenced by capitalism and socialism.

The gradual breakdown of political democracy, which was opposed by the left in Europe, its metamorphosis into pluralist democracy, the shift in the communist world, and the resurrection of linked republics were all inevitable outcomes of humanity's progress.

The democratic class conflict influenced the West in the 1950s, and it continued to damage people's democracies in the 2000s. France, Spain, Portugal, and socialist parties have all chosen the Scandinavian model of social democracy. With the socialist world's transition to multi-party democracy, communist parties evolved into socialist or social democratic parties (Bouthoul 1975).

5) Democracy Consciousness

Democracy is a way of living. It is a regime of virtues, rights, and liberties. Democracy does not imply that people divide into parties or fight in camps. Democracy is not about causing disturbance in society by forming class, sect, region, race, and interest groups. Parties are critical components of democracies, and they should provide solutions rather than problems.

Democracy is a regime for achieving social efficiency and progress in a free environment by believing in the rule of people, freedoms, and law, respecting the will of the people, and profiting from science, all under the auspices of a parliament constituted by the free will of the people. The fall of totalitarian governments with bottom-up waves, the termination of communist party monopolies, and the opening to political and economic pluralism are all manifestations of democratic awareness (Kapani, 1977).

Therefore, democracy is an event of consciousness. It is the institutionalization of the law. It signifies that institutions have constitutional standing. Pluralistic democracy endures because people trust the legislative system. Strengthening, deepening, and institutionalizing parliament is insufficient to produce democracy. Everyone, from bureaucrats to elected officials and voters, must be made aware of democratic principles.

The capacity of the legislative body to monitor the executive body boosts trust in the system. The political authority has always seen legislative and judicial oversight as a barrier to activity and has opposed it.

Uncontrolled political or numerical majority is the government's method of creating individual or collective rule. The legislative body must be a location where rights and law come first, and where issues and solutions are developed in response to societal aspirations and requirements. Having this insight requires morals and a feeling of duty. devotion to democracy, its rules, and institutions, rather than devotion to the leader and his preferences, is a necessary condition for the survival of democracy.

Democratic education is vital. Having opposing viewpoints is fundamental to the system. Education should provide the general public with an awareness of tolerance for other ideas and views. Democracy needs a free press, sensitive public opinion, responsible intellectuals-bureaucrats, lawmen with a sense of justice, and informed citizenry.

C. State, Personality of the State, State and Society

1) Meaning of State

The state, like all human societies, emerges and exists inside them. The state mechanism is made up of organs, authority, power, and people. The state is a structured network of relationships.

The state, a centuries-old social phenomena, is a notion with several perspectives and interpretations, but no one can agree on its definition.

In addition to theological and metaphysical explanations for its origin and birth, there are ideas and viewpoints that explain the notion from a hypothetical, historical, and sociological standpoint.

While some perceive the state primarily as a class system, others position it at the pinnacle of societal principles. Some regard the state as a means rather than an end; some see the state as the sole and dominant power structure; some argue that the state should collapse on its own, but that it should be abolished as soon as possible rather than waiting for this to happen; some see the state as an organized structure of a class; and some see the state as a supra-class unifying institution covering the entire society (Kongar 1972).

In addition to these beliefs that provide meaning to the state via ideological knowledge, jurists offer meaning in the context of an aspect of the state that they use as a foundation. According to one viewpoint, the state is a customized version of the country. According to one viewpoint, the state is a functional legal system. Another definition of a state is a political organization created by a community of people ruled by a supreme power with coercive powers that is

founded in a specific nation. According to another viewpoint, the state is an abstract term that cannot be seen or felt. It exists because people are thinking about it. The common definitions and interpretations are based on the state's foundational characteristics.

The issue of the state remains open. Why did people think about it, and why did they form such an organization? What drove them to build such a big and sophisticated network?

Whether one wants to comprehend and answer problems from a legal, theological, or political standpoint, explanation is ultimately based on assumptions. Determining thousands of years of history, as well as the sentiments, ideas, expectations, and ambitions of those who lived throughout that time, has resulted in the development of various hypotheses. However, it is apparent that the state and political communities arose at a later point in the historical process. The concept of the state emerges when authority becomes depersonalized and institutionalized. As a result of evolution, people have determined that obedience is appropriate not to personal sovereignty such as chief-bey-khan-khakan-overlord-sultan, but to the permanent and abstract entity known as the state above and beyond them, and have chosen the path of practice (Kapani, Kamu Hürriyetleri, 1981).

Historically, state development has followed this structure. Throughout this process, the state became the emblem of political unity and integration. Although the state is seen as a representation of legal fiction or myth, it is the power that is supported by actual, tangible facts and materials. Those in positions of authority made decisions on behalf of the state, established regulations, and enforced discipline via the use of force if needed. Furthermore, we must not mix administrators who operate on behalf of the state with administrators and entities that act on behalf of the state.

Even in its most rudimentary form, the state contains several features, including the distinction between ruler and ruled, the phenomena of political power, and its contemporary meaning and components. Again, the state in its present form is a new institution. From the past to the present, the state, the organization that maintains people together throughout the country and nation under many, scattered, and competing authorities, has undergone diversification in its organs and changes in the manner it exercises authority.

2) Personality of the State

The state survives via its material components and administrators who wield political authority. However, it is vital to highlight his distinct characteristics. There are varying perspectives on the state's distinct personality, character, and quality. Some of them recognize the state's legal and moral personality, while others regard the state as a living organism. Others argue that the state lacks legal or any other kind of personality, other than the physical existence and personality of the rulers, and that this is an empty fiction (Foster, 1975).

In addition to the state's legal personality, the remarks acknowledge it as well. Changes in rulers and regimes have little bearing on the state's long-term survival. The state's existence is unaffected by this alteration and will continue.

As a social reality, the state is the biggest, most developed, well-organized, and inclusive political entity. It is a state-run institution. The state provides the overall structure and personnel for political operations.

Without a doubt, the state is made out of its citizens. As a result, when the term "state order" is used, it refers to the individuals who create it. Similarly, when state power is stated, those who exercise it come to mind, and when state laws are mentioned, those who enact them come to mind. People having the capacity to maintain order, utilize authority, and create and execute laws have certain political inclinations, ideological orientations, and worldviews. Although it is stated that choices and actions undertaken on behalf of the state are in the public interest - for the good of society - it is clear that only certain classes and groups profit. This circumstance cannot be changed. Political choices receive societal legitimacy with the mark of the state. However, the governing power's political choices serve as the directing force.

Law has given the state a permanent foundation in the form of a fake legal organization. Administrators' status when exercising authority has been established. Managers cannot have subjective rights over authority (Freedman, 1989).

They only execute the powers lawfully conferred upon them as state entities. This term reflects the present situation of the law. On the contrary, it is apparent that knowledge and practices have no bearing on the rule of law and cannot be.

However, it is apparent that the personality of the state is related to sovereignty. It should be noted that sovereignty, which is regarded as the primary requirement for the fundamental parts of the state, evolved concurrently with the state in historical terms. Sovereignty is related to the notion of power.

3) State and Society

The state may be understood via its duty to the society in which it exists. What their responsibilities should be influences our perspective of individuals and society. Social unity refers to the unity of numerous groupings. Each group creates society via interest connections formed by economic, educational, and religious frameworks. The state's connection with society is defined by the activities and duties it does.

The scope and character of the state's job and duties in the interaction between state, society, and person have been the subject of many perspectives throughout history. Expectations within society are based on the expectations of certain groups within society. This is dependent on the impact of effective power group dynamics in society on the management system.

Just as religious organizations want to promote religious activity, economic power holders seek to grow activity, which defines the state's sphere of operation. The sphere of state action is also determined by the worker-peasant class's or union's perception of activity.

While the contraction of governmental powers resulted in the rise of the powers of economic power holders, the actions of other power holders were attempted to be balanced.

This is why the monist concept of the state gave way to the dualistic kind of economic and political order that shapes the state structure. Furthermore, the trade union movement and the

organizing actions of individuals who do business inside the state and society have shown the wide state framework (Garaudy, 1976).

Accelerating with an individualist approach, private capital, industrialization, economic power conglomeration, the economy's integration into a universal organization through cross-border mergers, and regional cooperation efforts have transformed the democratic state structure and functioning.

The societal notion of providing a balanced guarantee of personal rights and freedoms via the combination of economic and political power has received governmental protection with the recognition of social security as a constitutional right.

People have experimented with several state conceptions throughout history, including the protective state, state of law, just state, welfare state, social state, and religious state.

The social service state introduced the principles of planning and regulating the state, a shift from justice to welfare, and a pluralist interpretation, philosophy, and practice of the rule of law.

While multi-party pluralistic democracies and nations that have assimilated the notion of the rule of law recognize the need for limits, developing countries and single-party totalitarian regimes do not.

The state that will lead the people to peace, security, and prosperity must have self-governing norms, well defined borders, and limited authority.

Conclusion:

Since the day he was born, man has tried to engage with himself and the society he lives in, to understand it, and to find the ideal state structure created by it. There has been an understanding of human beings, a view of society, an interpretation of democracy and the state since the early periods. With this effort, humanity has determined scientific branches, areas of investigation and research.

The fact that the concepts of individual - society - democracy - state are flexible - uncertain and changeable, unlike the material world, has not made a development similar to the technological development in the material field possible. Undoubtedly, the perspective of those who put forward views and ideas in these fields and the meaning that this perspective gave to the concepts played a major role in this.

In ideal societies, democracy is the name of the regime that is open to thinking out loud. There can be no dogmatic, tutelary, oppressive, top-down democracy. In pluralistic democracies, there is an environment for idea generation and debate. Compared to other systems, democracy is a system of voting to stop those who aim to serve their own interests or the interests of a certain group.

The state is a systematic network of relations. Where there is government, there is politics. There is no supra-state state, but there are organizations created by international politics. The duties undertaken by the state have varied according to the structure of democracy and ideological structure. Basic and side duties have changed over time according to the needs of society.

The reality of exalted man and ideal society; It shows that social, political and economic problems can be solved and the future can be looked at with confidence through the democratic rule of law, liberalization of the economy and restructuring of the administration.

What should be known and remembered is that a person's problems can be overcome by making his inner world healthy. Realistic, consistent, balanced, human-society-democracy-state views and organizations will provide the desired environment.

RESTRICTION

This study is limited to previous scientific studies conducted around the world. Although the literature review was conducted within the existing framework, it was not forgotten that different geographical regions and cultural contexts were not evaluated from a broader

perspective. However, given this study's adoption of a specific methodology and time constraints, it may have limitations in overall validity.

NOTIFICATIONS

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external consultants.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declared no conflict of interest regarding this article.

Financial Support: The authors did not report any financial support related to this article.

ETHICAL STATEMENT

Publication ethics of our university's relevant regulations; It is a national-based scientific study that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, respect for the findings and creations of others, and works to achieve this, aiming at these principles in the field of relevant sciences.

Resource

Adivar, A. (1969). *Science and Religion Throughout History*. Istanbul: Remzi Bookstore.

Beer, M. (1965). *History of Socialism and Social Struggles*. Istanbul: Hüsnütabiat Printing House.

Blackburn, S. R. (1972). *Ideology in Social Science*. Fontane Books.

Boratav, K. (1973). *Developments in Socialist Planning*. Ankara: A.Ü.SBF c.

Bouthoul, G. (1975). *Political Sociology*. Istanbul: Development century.

Foster, M. A. (1975). *Warring World*. Istanbul: E Publications.

Freedman, B. (1989). *Environmental Ecology. Effects of Pollution and Other Stresses on Ecosystem Structure and Function*. San Diego: Academic Press.

Garaudy, R. (1976). *Socialism and Morality*. Istanbul: Process Publications.

Kapani, M. (1977). *Democratic Theory*. Ankara: A.Ü. Faculty of Law YY.

- Kapani, M. (1981). *Public Liberties*. Ankara: A.Ü. Faculty of Law YY.
- Kongar, E. (1972). *Social Change: theories, principles*. Ankara: Bilgi Publishing House.
- Malatyali, H. (2005). *Social Structure in the Hittites*. Baku: AIU.yy.
- Malatyali, H. (2006). Baku: Vector Int.Sciences Academy.
- Schonfield, H. (1972). *The Politics of God*. New York: Bentham Books Inc.
- Sorokin, P. (1972). *Social Philosophy in an Age of Crisis*. Istanbul: Information century.